

Behaviour theories literature review

Identification of constructs

Michie et al. (2014) include a multiple-page summary of each theory they review, and Kwon and Silva (2020) provide an Appendix that lists details about each theory. For theories that appeared in Michie et al., these summaries were used to complete database entries. We recorded basic information about the theory, such as its full name, authors, year published, associated discipline, and a brief summary. Each summary in Michie et al. (2014) begins with a bullet-pointed list of constructs involved; all constructs were entered in the database. For constructs that possibly would be coded as value-related, definitions drawn from the theory summaries were included in the database.

In Kwon and Silva's appendix, constructs were listed with less standardized means and fewer details. For theories only in Kwon and Silva's review (52 theories), a multi-step process was conducted to summarize constructs in each theory, in order to create construct lists analogous to those in Michie et al. (2014). This process involved four independent coders and two discussants/supervisors. The process was as follows.

1. Training phase:

- a. All researchers examined Michie et al.'s construct lists and theory summaries to understand the way in which the constructs were used, parsed, and organized. This helped the team to reproduce the Michie et al. construct lists as closely as possible.
- b. Four of the original manuscripts that presented theories (as identified by Kwon and Silva (2020)) were selected as "training manuscripts". These manuscripts were selected to represent diverse types of original sources (e.g., books and articles, from different disciplines).
- c. All coders and discussants/supervisors read and coded these training manuscripts. The coding process involved identifying constructs important to the theory's function, description, or process, then including direct quotes or paraphrases to define each construct.
- d. Coding results from all researchers were combined, with agreements and disagreements noted.
- e. All researchers discussed every construct and its definition until agreement was reached on a final list of constructs for each theory.

2. Coding phase:

- a. Teams of two coders read a subset of original manuscripts. Each coder independently identified the constructs and definitions for each theory.

- b. The two lists of constructs were compared, with agreements and disagreements noted.
- c. The two coders and one discussant/supervisor met and discussed each construct in each theory until consensus was reached. Where the two coders disagreed (e.g., one had identified a particular construct and the other had not), the three researchers discussed how to proceed (e.g., whether the construct should be included). The team often revisited the original manuscripts during this discussion.